

Participatory tools

COLLECTIVE FEEDBACK FACILITATION

PREPARING FOR IMPACT AND DISSEMINATION, DRAFTING DELIVERABLES: CREATE USEFUL CONTENT

How to ensure useful and usable deliverables?

To produce useful deliverables for users, involve them as early as possible in the creation process. The earlier users are involved, the better:

- The easier it is to take ownership
- The more the output will meet needs and expectations and be useful and used.
- Be prepared to adapt the project according to feedback and needs if possible.

How to solve it

At the beginning, it helps to collect the needs of the users. Users need to see the benefits of getting involved.

Throughout the project, you need to regularly contact a targeted group of users to get feedback at different key stages of the project.

In general, you involve the diversity of potential users and adapt the involvement to the types of users.

Word of advice

When gathering needs and feedback on the production concept, you adapt your presentation to the users and be clear. A concrete example often helps in understanding a concept. Finding the right balance not to bias the feedback while making sure the concept is understood is key.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Collective feedback facilitation – Everyone has something to add to the building.

Description of the tool

- **What:** collect points of view and opinions on a first draft/prototype/concept, identify the needs of future users, build an adapted production together.
- **How long:** 1 to 2h
- **How many:** 4 to 12
- **What you'll need:** sticky notes, markers

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

Steps:

- The facilitator presents the elements to discuss in a way that is both clear enough for participants to understand and open enough not to bias their feedback
- Participants use sticky notes to give their feedback. The facilitator can help them by giving specific categories, such as:
 - Positive aspects, something to improve, a limit,
 - Different sub-topics,
- The facilitator gathers the ideas and asks for clarification—the participants exchange.
- If needed, the facilitator can ask the participants to prioritise the topics, the improvements, and the key elements.

Testimony of the use

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In the WP5 of LIAISON, some assessment methods were developed collectively with end-users. The meeting aimed to get feedback on a first draft and build the method together. In this example, the collective feedback facilitation was conducted online (with the tool MURAL) with 4 participants.

It allows for evaluation of progress and confirmation of the work done. It works well if there is a need and if everyone is interested. Doing this, you collect everyone's individual opinions. It allows you to develop useful tools for the field.

Participants embraced the method, and it aroused interest.

Tips:

- Familiarize yourself with the platform beforehand
- Adapt to the audience's knowledge of the subject
 - If there is little knowledge, make the presentation clear but general and open enough so as not to bias the feedback
 - If knowledge is plentiful, keep the presentation as short as possible while keeping the instructions clear
- Categories the types of feedback (themes, questions) to structure and not forget anything
- But allow general/open feedback at first
- Adapt according to the type of audience (if not used to this type of exercise, guiding can help)

Another tool: Six Thinking Hats ([Tools for knowledge and Learning](#); tool 28, [The MSP tool guide](#))

